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SCHOOL CURRICULUM: ORGANIZATION OF KNOWLEDGE AND DEVELOPMENT OF LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The present study approaches the study in relation to the school curriculum and pursues to reflect the curriculum in the organization of educational knowledge, and its curriculum importance in the accomplishment of the performance of the essential learnings to the students. It emphasizes the need to construct a school curriculum that is collectively, democratically, that contemplates values, respect for diversity, and concrete, structured and meaningful learning with a socializing function of the non-fragmented one that values the cultural, social and educational historical construction. The main objective is to understand the importance and comprehensiveness of the school curriculum in meaningful student learning, both in the formal context and in the informal context. During the research, it was possible to understand that the school curriculum is a significant axis in the achievement of goals established by the school, which must be rethought, analyzed and constructed collectively, in the search for a constructive teaching-learning, as close as possible to life and social reality of students.

KEYWORDS: School curriculum. Organization of Knowledge. Learning.

INTRODUCTION

This article aims to analyze the importance of the school curriculum in the educational, social and cultural sphere, with the school curriculum being a set knowledge, which must be critically analyzed, as well as its influence on the achievement of students' teaching and learning objectives. Making it necessary for the school, together with teachers, parents and school community in general, are able to analyze, understand and verify, that the school curriculum is a valuable element in the school environment and in planning activities developed by the teacher and students, which allows a better organization of content and activities to be worked on by the teacher. The school team needs to understand, through moments of study and analysis, that the curriculum goes beyond the understanding of isolated subjects, of fragmented content and passive knowledge. Curricular teaching needs to be based on appreciation, by everyone who makes up the school team, aiming to provide significant points in expanding and implementing knowledge constructive, contributing to critical, active, reflective and structured in different social contexts. Through this study it is possible to understand and analyze the understanding of the ideas of some scholars who deepened the studies on the topic, as well as the current Brazilian Educational Legislation, in seeking to verify what solutions and knowledge can be obtained to develop a more solid and comprehensive awareness of the importance of the school curriculum in the educational context and in the meaningful learning of students, if understood as an important part of the organization of school knowledge, its organization became necessary with the emergence of schooling in mass, there was a need for standardization of the knowledge to be taught, that is, for the content requirements to be the same. It is clear the importance and breadth of the school curriculum, in the social, cultural and educational lives of students and in the teaching-learning process, as well as in the construction of knowledge solid, critical, reflective, and fluent skills for living well and interpreting society.

The school curriculum is part of the history of Brazilian education, the same has undergone

debates, transformations, changes, and modifications countless times in the educational context, over the years, since the education established by the Jesuits.

Nowadays, it plays an important role in the formal environment, as it is an indispensable and essential tool for knowledge and social transformation, cultural, educational and teaching in all forms of Brazilian Education. O school curriculum must have a collective, inclusive and never neutral basis and structure, providing the student with access to the body of knowledge historically produced, both for the student's school life and for their social life, has to be looked at by educators in a different way, much more than a simple curriculum to be followed, but an ethical commitment in teaching learning, in the search to investigate and reflect on issues of a theoretical and practices that guide pedagogical practice aimed at meeting the demands of current affairs, and mainly the cultural diversity present in the different areas educational.

SCHOOL CURRICULUM: ORGANIZATION OF KNOWLEDGE

The word curriculum, which derives from the Latin curriculum, (originating from the Latin verb currere, which means to run) and refers to the course, the route, the path of life or activities of a person or group of people (GORDON apud FERRAÇO, 2005, p. 54). This is, therefore, the path that every student must follow when throughout Basic Education. The School Curriculum represents the journey that the student will take through throughout their school life, both in relation to appropriate content and the activities carried out under the systematization of the School. In this sense Coll, (1997) says: "the curriculum is a project that presides over school educational activities, defines their intentions and provides appropriate and useful action guides for teachers, who are directly responsible for its execution".

It is important to highlight that the school curriculum has a socializing function in educational scope, and cannot be analyzed as a set of disciplines and fragmented content, and must

be prepared in order to provide conditions of knowledge for students aiming to cover and meet the diverse social and cultural realities in a broad, real, meaningful, reflective, democratic, inclusive, ethical and moral. For Moreira and Candau (2007, p.18), the Curriculum “can be understood as the school experiences that unfold around the knowledge in the midst of social relations that contribute to the construction of identities of our students.”

The Federal Constitution of 1988, in its article 201, provides for the adoption of the school curriculum across all educational institutions in the country, ensuring that all students have access to a series of fixed content, considered minimum for basic training. “Minimum contents will be set for teaching fundamental, in order to ensure common basic training and respect for the values cultural and artistic, national and regional”. (BRAZIL, 1988)

The National Education Guidelines and Bases Law, nº 9,394 of 20 December 1996, indicates that it is up to the school to prepare its pedagogical proposal and identifies the general outlines for the organization of pedagogical work in schools. In article 27 of the LDB, which deals with basic education, we can highlight the following guidelines regarding the contents of the school curricula of the basic education.

Art. 27. The curricular contents of basic education will also comply with the following Guidelines:

- I – the dissemination of values fundamental to social interest, the rights and duties of citizens, respect for the common good and the democratic order;
- II – consideration of the students’ education conditions in each establishment;
- III – work orientation;
- IV – promotion of educational sport and support for non-formal sporting practices.

From 1997 onwards, with the discussion of the National Curricular Guidelines (DCNs) the National Curriculum Parameters were developed,

as a reference for each discipline and served as a reference for the renewal and re-elaboration of the school’s curricular proposal until the definition of the Curricular Guidelines. Resolution CNE/CEB, nº04 of 13/07/2010, defines the Curricular Guidelines General National Bases for Basic Education and reinforces the creation of a National Base Common Curricular for all Basic Education and defines it as: “Knowledge, culturally produced knowledge and values, expressed in public policies {...}”. After a broad debate throughout Brazil, in 2013, the Curricular Guidelines National Standards (DCNs) were defined as mandatory standards for Basic Education, with the aim of guiding the curriculum planning of schools and education systems teaching, began to guide the minimum curricula and content. Therefore, the guidelines ensure basic training, based on the Education Guidelines and Bases Law (LDB), which originated it, article 9, item IV:

IV - establish, in collaboration with the States, the Federal District and the Municipalities, competencies and guidelines for early childhood education, primary education and secondary education, which will guide the curricula and their minimum contents, in order to ensure common basic training;

In 2014, with the approval of the National Education Plan (PNE), it was placed as The goal is to develop the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) for all of Brazil. Its intention is to raise teaching standards in all regions, reducing inequality in student performance. The essential knowledge that students from all schools in the country must learn year by year in Basic Education were defined by the National Base Common Curricular (BNCC), approved in 2017. The BNCC is the guiding document mandatory that gathers references for the preparation of CVs, establishing learning and development objectives for all students. In this perspective, presents the objectives and how the areas of knowledge and disciplines they must organize themselves for their guarantee.

The National Common Curricular Base

(2017) explains what you want to achieve, the municipalities will define the paths, proposals and strategies to reach this result. These will necessarily be particular, responding to the context of each region and community. That is, the curriculum is the set of experiences that are constructed and offered in the daily life of schools, always in a dialogical relationship between teachers and students. From the perspective of integral education, the curriculum builds from the student, assuming the multidimensionality and singularity of each one.

Furthermore, BNCC and curricula have complementary roles to ensure the essential learning defined for each stage of Basic Education, since such learning only materializes through the set of decisions that characterize the curriculum in action. It is these decisions that will adapt the BNCC's propositions to the local reality, considering the autonomy of the education systems or networks and school institutions, as well as the context and characteristics of the students. (BRAZIL, p. 16, 2017)

Even after Brazil developed and approved the Common National Base Curricular (BNCC), 2017, the National Curricular Guidelines (DCNs), 2013, continue to be valid because the documents are complementary: the Guidelines give the structure, the Base the detailing of content and skills.

In all these documents, which guide Brazilian education, the definition of curriculum and its construction, underwent intense and long-term research, with debate between educators and other professionals in the field, always with the aim of increasingly ensure quality education for all students in the country.

The curriculum must have a formative, educational, social and cultural function, it must be understood as a practice of transforming reality and knowledge concrete. It needs to be debated and analyzed constantly by all those who make up

the school team, in a broad dimension as a way of appropriating the social experience accumulated and worked on from the formal knowledge that school selects, organizes and proposes the focus of school activities.

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SCHOOL CURRICULUM IN THE PERFORMANCE OF ACTIVITIES ESSENTIAL LEARNINGS FOR STUDENTS

The School Curriculum represents the journey that the student will take through throughout their school life, both in relation to appropriate content and the activities carried out under the systematization of the School. In this sense Coll, (1997) states that: "the curriculum is a project that presides over school educational activities, defines their intentions and provides appropriate and useful action guides for teachers, who are directly responsible for its execution".

School curricula are a construction and selection of knowledge and practices produced in the real context of society, covering social issues, political, cultural, ethical and pedagogical. Therefore, in addition to the selected contents, must take into account the needs of students, their social reality and cultural diversity, as established in article 26 of LDB n° 9,394, December 20 1996.

Primary and secondary education curricula must have a common national base, to be complemented, in each education system and school establishment, by a diversified part, required by the regional and local characteristics of society, culture, economy and clientele. (BRAZIL, 1996)

The school curriculum has long ceased to be just an area merely technique, focused on issues relating to procedures, techniques and methods. Contents and activities must contribute to the cognitive and emotional intelligence of students students, promoting complete training with development of skills and the ability to apply knowledge. Skills no cognitive skills such as socialization, cooperation,

resilience and curiosity must also be explored based on students' natural abilities. Learn from exploration and thinking about different types of phenomena, becoming the most active in learning in the cognitive, physical, social, and artistic fields, enabling the growth of autonomy.

The educational context has undergone major changes and transformations and the school must provide students with opportunities to acquire cognitive skills considered necessary by society, prepare them to the world of work and life in society, and also develop your talents individuals, having a greater commitment to intellectual and moral formation. O school curriculum is part of the history of Brazilian education, therefore it is historic, and has also undergone transformations, debates and changes countless times in the context educational.

The school curriculum is very significant in educational practice, in everyday life. educational context, is an important element within the school context, an axis to achieve the objectives proposed by the school, is one of the documents that guide the teacher's work, it must be in accordance with the political Project pedagogical framework, national curricular guidelines, the National Common Curricular Base and other documents that guide Brazilian education.

It is necessary to admit that the school curriculum is not an innocent and neutral element of disinterested transmission of social knowledge, it cannot be neglected in educational processes that aim to address the cultural characteristics of the intended students. It must not contain only content, but have a collective and inclusive base and structure, seek to promote interdisciplinarity and include actions aimed at intellectual, social and affective of students, providing access to the set of knowledge historically produced, making an ethical commitment in teaching and learning, in the search to investigate and reflect on issues of a theoretical and practical nature that guide pedagogical practice aimed at meeting the demands of current affairs and especially the cultural diversity present in educational institutions, increasing the quality of education offered.

To get a quality education it is necessary to analyze the curriculum school, as it affects the student's development, considering it in line with the historical, cultural, social, active, democratic and critical reality of the community. We need to make the necessary adjustments to keep up with the changes, implementing teaching and learning, where today's students are increasingly free, autonomous and independent.

The National Common Curricular Base (2017) provides in its guidelines the focuses on the demands of contemporary society that imposes an innovative and inclusive of central issues of the educational process.

In the new world scenario, recognizing oneself in its historical and cultural context, communicating, being creative, analytical-critical, participatory, open to the new, collaborative, resilient, productive and responsible requires much more than the accumulation of information. It requires the development of skills to learn to learn, know how to deal with increasingly available information, act with discernment and responsibility in the contexts of digital cultures, apply knowledge to solve problems, have autonomy to make decisions, be proactive to identify data from a situation and seek solutions, live with and learn from differences and diversities. (BRAZIL, 2017, p.12)

The purpose of the school curriculum encompasses not only the propagation of culture, but social transformation. In this sense, it is clear that the school curriculum is more what a schedule of disciplines, but an instrument filled with inspiration ideological, political, social and cultural. The educator must be aware of the different contexts in which curricular proposals are created, as this is the instrument intervention and defense of proposals consistent with education and Society fair, inclusive and democratic.

For Moreira and Candau (2007), the teacher has a fundamental role in preparation of school curricula.

The curriculum is, in other words, the heart of the school, the central space in which we all act, which makes us, at different levels of the educational process, responsible for its elaboration. The role of the educator in the curricular process is, therefore, fundamental. He is one of the great architects, whether he likes it or not, of the construction of the curricula that are systematized in schools and classrooms. (MOREIRA and CANDAU, 2007, p. 19).

The school curriculum must be used to enable social transformation, understanding the differences and contemplating the multiplicity of individuals who make up the same school space, including values and principles, as the school needs to form citizens with critical awareness, for human knowledge and scientific knowledge, then, must be respected, valued collectively and democratically in the educational and social context, as it provides opportunities for the implementation of social actions, cultural and educational in educational institutions.

METHODOLOGY

In the search to understand school curriculum, influence on the organization of educational knowledge, and its importance in achieving performance of essential learning for students, this article presents a methodology used to develop the research, the theoretical approach, in which demonstrates the description of the object of investigation and the strategies for data collection, as well as the way in which they were treated. It is a bibliographical research, prepared using already published material, consisting of mainly from books, laws, periodical articles and materials made available on the internet, which demonstrate the challenges of the school curriculum and its influence on achievement of teaching learning objectives for students, guiding the definition of essential learning and not just minimum content to be taught.

It is a study of a qualitative nature, developed through reading, precise knowledge, reflection, and based on critical analysis, which enabled a

significant and constructive deepening of the school curriculum and its importance in the organization of knowledge and the development of students' learning students, according to Silva and Menezes (2005, p.20), qualitative research "considers that there is a dynamic relationship between the real world and the subject, that is, a inseparable link between the objective world and the subjectivity of the subject who cannot be translated into numbers."

CONCLUSION

During the development of this study, it was analyzed that the school curriculum is much more than a simple grid of isolated subjects, of content fragmented and passive knowledge that must appear in the school environment and yes, it should be treated and discussed as a tool that allows clarity and lucidity in the organization of knowledge, methods, resources, adaptations, as we live in a complex world, which cannot be completely explained by a single angle, but from a multifaceted vision, constructed by the views of the different knowledge areas. The organization of the curriculum should seek to enable greater interdisciplinarity and contextualization, ensuring free communication between all areas favoring the development of essential learning to students, involving environmental, political, economic, social, cultural issues and educational. Reflection by the entire school team in organizing the curriculum school, it needs to lead teachers and students to review pedagogical practices and reversing some traditional teaching and learning models. It becomes more and more It is more necessary to adapt the school curriculum to the social and historical reality of students, in the search to value cultural and social differences and develop a social, cultural, affective and human formation of all students, in a democratic, inclusive, ethical and moral.

The school curriculum cannot be seen as static, on the contrary, it was and continues to be built. Reflecting on this is important, because, as states Veiga (2002, p. 7), "the analysis and understanding of the production process of school knowledge expands understanding of curricular issues".

The school curriculum is an indispensable instrument in the organization of knowledge and pedagogical work and school as a social function, must provide necessary basis for understanding, reflection, and appropriation of the curriculum school in a sensitized and appropriate way, if well planned and elaborated collectively with the participation of the school community, certainly the school will be able to develop critical, reflective, autonomous, and intentional learning based on precise pedagogical and epistemological knowledge.

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